

Table S1. Sample portion of Hypocentre table that has hypocentre quality parameters

YR	MODY	HRMN	SEC	LATITUDE	LONGITUDE	DEPTH	MAG	NO	RMSRES	x	y	GAP	DMIN	RZDM	NP	NS	SE_OT	SE_H	SE_Z	Q
2007	0101	0020	12.29	-38.9440	177.9769	33.64	2.10	5	0.03	143.01	-513.20	287	26	1.3	3	2	0.16	1.53	1.63	E
2007	0101	0058	55.18	-37.8333	176.8147	7.58	1.70	6	0.18	-12.67	-549.88	271	16	0.5	4	2	0.43	1.86	5.65	E
2007	0101	0125	15.11	-36.2665	179.8205	12.00	3.70	6	0.06	97.56	-849.99	340	218	0.1	4	2	99.00	99.00	20.00	E
2007	0101	0201	49.40	-37.7321	178.2632	55.47	2.50	5	0.04	82.31	-636.15	173	18	3.1	3	2	0.19	1.32	2.12	E
2007	0101	0442	47.32	-36.2197	179.2004	35.00	0.00	7	0.12	166.37	-905.81	335	249	0.1	5	2	0.10	1.78	20.00	E
2007	0101	0514	53.91	-37.6065	177.3265	131.00	2.70	5	0.03	7.83	-597.38	241	84	1.6	3	2	0.21	6.45	4.87	E
2007	0101	0522	10.56	-41.2961	174.8415	28.21	1.90	7	0.03	91.92	-142.78	229	6	4.7	5	2	0.15	1.07	1.15	D
2007	0101	0550	8.49	-40.9413	175.6590	16.33	1.90	8	0.06	121.10	-216.37	165	27	0.6	6	2	0.07	0.42	1.39	C
2007	0101	0607	54.41	-39.5233	176.0160	37.42	1.90	8	0.08	47.66	-358.98	270	24	1.6	6	2	0.29	1.44	1.75	D
2007	0101	0608	19.48	-40.1245	174.9440	35.01	2.30	10	0.13	17.22	-249.64	143	38	0.9	7	3	0.06	0.51	1.27	C
2007	0101	0651	39.52	-44.6107	167.6373	30.64	2.60	12	0.15	-107.65	521.27	203	35	0.9	8	4	0.07	0.88	0.48	C
2007	0101	0830	11.80	-39.4753	175.6770	24.29	2.30	33	0.11	21.45	-345.14	117	9	2.7	29	4	0.03	0.34	0.40	A
2007	0101	0925	56.64	-37.2128	177.4926	15.00	2.70	8	0.15	-6.99	-641.10	193	48	0.3	6	2	0.14	0.89	1.57	C
2007	0101	0946	51.08	-41.8462	174.1127	14.07	2.10	10	0.09	83.16	-57.07	160	22	0.6	8	2	0.08	0.55	0.86	C
2007	0101	1024	54.12	-45.1585	166.8927	30.04	2.10	7	0.08	-107.62	606.08	257	41	0.7	4	3	0.09	0.65	0.96	D
2007	0101	1049	20.29	-45.1766	166.7472	21.29	2.40	7	0.20	-114.41	615.55	295	45	0.5	5	2	0.27	1.90	2.56	E
2007	0101	1115	57.99	-35.3627	179.8773	271.31	3.60	7	0.19	42.58	-934.51	344	283	1.0	5	2	0.34	5.47	6.99	E
2007	0101	1144	4.95	-39.4585	175.7146	21.03	2.20	31	0.11	22.83	-348.61	93	22	1.0	25	6	0.03	0.40	0.56	A
2007	0101	1206	59.97	-40.8695	174.3125	52.81	2.30	16	0.05	27.58	-151.66	150	34	1.6	12	4	0.06	0.26	0.61	B
2007	0101	1301	6.05	-38.3215	176.2885	6.44	2.20	10	0.15	-15.92	-478.71	137	8	0.8	8	2	0.07	0.74	1.08	C
2007	0101	1304	48.02	-38.3196	176.2964	5.00	1.60	7	0.05	-15.51	-479.30	144	6	0.8	4	3	1.56	47.06	20.00	E
2007	0101	1407	37.68	-39.8779	174.6012	104.53	2.70	25	0.10	-22.75	-252.59	137	36	2.9	19	6	0.04	0.46	0.90	A
2007	0101	1420	56.62	-38.2762	179.0251	10.20	2.20	5	0.08	172.25	-627.41	305	74	0.1	3	2	0.12	3.41	3.09	E
2007	0101	1422	11.59	-41.0463	172.4458	5.00	2.30	9	0.14	-80.65	-36.12	161	25	0.2	6	3	0.14	0.78	2.63	C
2007	0101	1424	28.63	-40.1682	176.5176	51.35	2.20	6	0.03	125.57	-328.85	168	32	1.6	3	3	0.06	1.02	1.40	D
2007	0101	1427	44.43	-45.1508	166.9118	34.68	2.30	7	0.07	-107.14	604.42	261	37	0.9	4	3	0.16	1.01	1.34	D
2007	0101	1615	44.88	-45.2321	167.2844	79.06	3.20	17	0.09	-79.78	590.46	194	29	2.7	14	3	0.09	0.69	0.69	C
2007	0101	1618	56.48	-39.1030	177.7056	20.42	2.00	5	0.14	134.83	-484.92	276	16	1.3	3	2	0.45	10.57	20.00	E
2007	0101	1658	56.42	-45.1655	167.3857	117.71	2.70	12	0.05	-79.20	579.59	185	38	3.1	9	3	0.08	0.54	0.71	C
2007	0101	1743	46.75	-38.1578	175.9668	195.76	3.70	22	0.07	-49.32	-475.65	244	100	2.0	20	2	0.11	1.02	0.87	D
2007	0101	1803	17.59	-45.0487	167.4453	124.92	2.90	15	0.13	-84.84	566.97	187	52	2.4	12	3	0.13	0.88	1.23	C
2007	0101	1804	33.63	-45.0406	167.5367	81.00	2.60	13	0.16	-80.27	561.31	179	52	1.6	10	3	0.08	0.71	0.73	B
2007	0101	1908	13.83	-44.1336	168.6479	3.58	2.20	9	0.04	-85.50	427.28	256	13	0.3	7	2	0.08	0.70	0.55	D
2007	0101	1932	5.79	-37.8353	176.8098	6.36	2.10	11	0.04	-12.87	-549.44	204	21	0.3	7	4	0.07	0.39	0.55	C
2007	0101	2101	53.38	-39.2692	175.1789	18.63	2.40	33	0.12	-26.41	-336.36	70	16	1.2	30	3	0.03	0.25	0.50	B
2007	0101	2104	21.96	-37.9009	176.3388	132.19	3.10	7	0.19	-41.17	-518.25	284	79	1.7	5	2	0.39	10.16	8.44	E
2007	0101	2104	30.10	-43.0670	171.4153	5.00	2.30	10	0.08	1.08	189.56	103	55	0.1	7	3	0.06	0.34	0.91	D
2007	0101	2106	0.40	-41.3937	173.6563	60.27	2.90	26	0.10	21.89	-71.74	76	24	2.5	23	3	0.02	0.27	0.32	B